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Updated wild boar hunting yield abundance model at European scale

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Abstract

The aim of this report is to model the hunting yield (HY) density of wild boar across their distribution range in Europe using updated data by January 2026. As with previous HY-based models, the response variable was the maximum annual number of wild boar hunted during the 2015–2025 hunting seasons, divided by the area (km²) of the corresponding administrative or management unit (HY density). The data therefore represent the maximum potential, generally prior to the arrival of ASF in the affected countries. High-resolution spatial data over data series were prioritised. The model was statistically downscaled to make predictions for 10x10 km squares. Secondly, to calibrate the model output into densities (i.e. to predict wild boar density values), we used local wild boar densities (individuals per km², n = 110 values), which were considered reliable and obtained within the framework of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW). As with the HY model, the calibration plots showed good linear predictive performance, and our results were consistent with the expected abundance distribution of wild boar. The present model improves upon previous models in terms of prediction in northern areas (Fennoscandia), as expected due to the availability of higher-resolution data. The same pattern is maintained in southern Europe, where higher quality data has previously been consistently collected by *ENETWILD*. Therefore, predictions based on recent historical hunting yields (manual maximum) stabilised (new data does not manifestly improve predictions). However, the prediction pattern for large parts of Central Europe (mainly France and Germany) remains inconsistent due to the continued lack of high-resolution HY data, indicating the need to engage potential data providers in these regions of Europe and overcome issues, which has been addressed in a separate report.

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¹ www.enetwild.com

Key words: distribution, density, hunting bags, population abundance, population monitoring, risk assessment, spatial modelling, wild boar, *Sus scrofa*, European Observatory of Wildlife

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Summary

Background and objectives:

ENETWILD has continued to collect data on hunting yield (HY) for wild boar across Europe at different spatial resolutions (e.g. hunting grounds, municipalities and NUTS3 regions), including wild boar. The aim of this report is to model the HY density of wild boar using updated data by January 2026. As with previous HY-based models, the response variable was the maximum annual number of wild boar hunted during the 2015–2025 hunting seasons, divided by the area (km²) of the relevant administrative or management unit (HY density), with a focus on using high-resolution spatial data. HY-based models were statistically downscaled to make predictions for 10x10 km squares. Secondly, we calibrated the model output to predict wild boar density.

Data:

We used maximum HY data compiled from records in accordance with the *ENETWILD* Data Model for the period 2015–2025. The data therefore represent the maximum potential, generally prior to the arrival of ASF in the affected countries.

We used predictions of relative abundance (i.e. number of hunted individuals per km²) at 10x10 km for wild boar, as well as local wild boar density (i.e. number of individuals per km²), to calibrate the model output into densities. This allowed us to predict wild boar density values (i.e. number of individuals per km²). A total of 110 density values were considered reliable and obtained within the framework of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW).

Modelling:

As with previous models based on HY, the response variable was the maximum number of wild boar hunted annually during the 2015–2025 hunting seasons, divided by the area (km²) of the relevant administrative or management unit (HY density). We conducted a negative binomial generalised linear model (GLMNB), including eco-geographical variables as predictors. As in previous *ENETWILD* reports, we considered explanatory variables describing climate, land cover, topography and human disturbance. Model projections were limited to exclude regions whose environmental conditions were deemed insufficiently represented by the training dataset.

To calibrate the HY-based model to densities, the median values of the predicted densities of hunted animals were extracted at 15 km buffers for each location (n = 110).

Results and discussion:

As with the HY model, the calibration plots showed monotonic relationships and good predictive performance for wild boar. Overall, our results were consistent with the expected abundance distribution of wild boar. As expected, the present model improves upon previous models in terms of prediction in northern areas (Fennoscandia) due to the availability of higher-resolution data. The same pattern was observed in southern Europe, where high quality data (in terms of spatial resolution and coverage) had previously been consistently collected by *ENETWILD*. Therefore, predictions based on recent historical hunting yields stabilised (new data does not significantly improve predictions already). However, the prediction pattern for large parts of Central Europe (mainly France and Germany) remains inconsistent due to the continued lack of high-resolution HY data. This indicates the need to engage with potential data providers in these regions and overcome the associated issues. This has been addressed in a separate report.

Conclusions and next steps:

- The updated HY-based wild boar model provides an improved and operationally relevant representation of abundance patterns across Europe, consolidating its role as a reference layer for risk assessment and wildlife management.
- First, the model confirms improved predictive performance in regions where high-resolution and recent hunting yield data are available, particularly in Fennoscandia, while also demonstrating the stability of predictions in southern Europe where long-term datasets already exist. This indicates that the modelling framework is mature and that future gains will primarily depend on data improvements rather than methodological changes.
- Second, the persistence of prediction uncertainty in Central Europe highlights the critical importance of engaging new data providers and improving spatial resolution of hunting statistics in these regions. Addressing this gap represents the main priority for future model refinement and for achieving a more homogeneous European coverage.
- Third, the successful calibration of HY predictions into density estimates substantially enhances the applicability of the model, allowing its integration into spatial risk analyses for African swine fever and other wildlife-related epidemiological processes. The model therefore represents a key component of the European wildlife analytical infrastructure.

Future work should focus on:

- Expanding the network of reliable density estimates for calibration,
- Improving temporal consistency to enable trend analyses,
- Strengthening collaboration with data providers in under-represented regions, and
- Maintaining regular model updates as new data become available.

Overall, the present update demonstrates that the *ENETWILD* modelling framework is operationally robust and scalable, and that continued investment in data harmonisation and provider engagement will be the main driver of future improvements

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1. Introduction

a. Background and Terms of Reference as provided by the requestor

This contract/grant was awarded by EFSA to: Università degli Studi di Torino (UNITO). Contract/Grant title: Wildlife and One Health: wildlife ecology, health surveillance and interaction with livestock, human population and environment, contract number: OC/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01.

This report covers work package 4.1A of specific contract 03, which details the production of wildlife abundance models at European scale, including an update model for wild boar abundance by December 2025 based on hunting data. This report complements the reports entitled "Using the latest data to model wild boar abundance at high resolution", which provides an update on the estimated wild boar distribution and abundance based on the most up to date density and occurrence data in Europe, and "A comparison of environmental and spatially explicit hunting-yield models for continuous gradient of relative abundance of wild boar in Europe", which evaluates a new approach for modelling gradual spatial changes in wild boar relative abundance using spatially explicit models. This report is to be published on Zenodo and should include R scripts of the model properly documented and map of each species individually stored.

b. Scope of the report

The *ENETWILD* consortium (www.enetwild.com) implemented an EFSA funded project whose main objective has been the collection of information regarding the geographical distribution and abundance of wild boar and other wild ungulates throughout Europe to subsequently create geospatial tools to be used in further risk assessment of diseases, such as ASF in the case of wild boar.

ENETWILD consortium, Croft et al (2024) used HYs of wild boar, as well as reliable wild boar density values over Europe, mainly from the EOW as a basis for the calibration of hunting yield-based model into densities. They use the predictions of hunting yields from the 2x2 model for wild boar by *ENETWILD* consortium (2022). Nowadays, this HY calibrated model into densities is the reference model recommended for use at European level at high resolution (2 x 2 km).

During the last years the consortium *ENETWILD* has continued collecting data on HY for wild boar over Europe at different spatial resolution (e.g., hunting ground, municipalities, NUT3). The first goal of this report is modelling HY density of wild boar with updated data by January 2026. Like previous models based on HY, the response variable is the maximum number of wild boar annually hunted in 2015-2025 hunting seasons divided by the area (km²) of the corresponding administrative unit (HY density). Secondly, as a basis for the calibration model output into densities (i.e. predicting density values of wild boar), we use the predictions of the HY-based model for wild boar and local wild boar densities (individuals per km²) considered reliable and obtained in the framework of the EOW, as well as some from recent literature (2015 onwards).

2. Methodology and data

a. Data

Wild boar HY data were incorporated for modelling from the *ENETWILD* data collection. Like previous reports, we focused on maximum hunting yield records from 2015 to 2025 hunting seasons. The response variable was obtained by dividing the maximum number of hunted animals by the area of the respective territorial unit (km²), i.e., we modelled HY density of wild boar. Hunting yield density records were transformed to density data multiplying their values by 10000 for modelling purposes (to have integer response variable for the negative binomial models).

According to previous reports (e. g., *ENETWILD* consortium et al., 2022) we selected environmental variables closely related to wild boar distribution describing topography, climate, land cover and human density (Table 1). Bioclimatic variables and sun radiation were obtained from the Worldclim 2 project database (<https://worldclim.org/version2>). Land use data was downloaded from ESA/CCI-LC project, version v2.0.7 (2015) (<https://www.esa-landcover-cci.org/?q=node/158>). Mean altitude was extracted from the USGS Space Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) GL30 (<https://lta.cr.usgs.gov/SRTM1Arc>) and snow cover was obtained from MODIS/Terra Snow Cover project (Monthly L3 Global 0.05Deg CMG, Version 6; <https://nsidc.org/data/MOD10CM>). Human footprint index was provided by The Last of the Wild Project version 2 (<http://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/data/collection/wildareas-v2>), while vegetation growing period was obtained from the Agro-Ecological Zones project (FAO; <http://www.appolutelydigital.com/DataPrimer/part154.html>). The bioclimatic regionalization described in previous reports (*ENETWILD* consortium et al., 2019a) was maintained for the study area. According to expert evaluations, in earlier reports some wrong predictions of wild boar abundance were in *Eucalyptus* spp. plantations mainly in West Europe. Those plantations are often considered like forests by telemetry-derived cartographic variables, and suitability indexes calculated for those areas can be misleading. For this reason, in the HY models we considered as predictor the percentage of *Eucalyptus* spp. as dominant species obtained from Brus et al. (2011) (European Forest Institute <https://www.efi.int/knowledge/maps/treespecies>). Raster predictor layers and grid polygons were managed using QGIS 3.22.9, tidyverse (Wickham et al., 2019) and *sf* (Pebesma, 2018) R packages.

Table 1. Variables used to model (i) the spatial pattern of wild ruminant abundance and (ii) distribution based on hunting yield and occurrence data, respectively.

Code	Variable description	Code	Variable description
BIO1	Annual mean temperature	lc_10	Cropland, rainfed
BIO2	Mean diurnal range (mean of monthly (max temp - min temp))	lc_11	Herbaceous cover
BIO3	Isothermality (BIO2/BIO7) (x 100)	lc_12	Tree or shrub cover
BIO4	Temperature seasonality (SD x 100)	lc_20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding
BIO5	Max temperature of warmest month	lc_30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover)

			(<50%)
BIO6	Min temperature of coldest month	lc_40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)
BIO7	Temperature annual range (BIO5-BIO6)	lc_60	Tree cover, broad-leaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
BIO8	Mean temperature of the Wettest Quarter	lc_61	Tree cover, broad-leaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)
BIO9	Mean temperature of the Driest Quarter	lc_70	Tree cover, needle leaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
BIO10	Mean temperature of warmest quarter	lc_71	Tree cover, needle leaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)
BIO11	Mean temperature of coldest quarter	lc_80	Tree cover, needle leaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
BIO12	Annual precipitation	lc_90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needle leaved)
BIO13	Precipitation of wettest month	lc_100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)
BIO14	Precipitation of driest month	lc_110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)
BIO15	Precipitation seasonality (coefficient of variation)	lc_120	Shrubland
BIO16	Precipitation of wettest quarter	lc_122	Deciduous shrubland
BIO17	Precipitation of driest quarter	lc_130	Grassland
BIO18	Precipitation of Warmest Quarter	lc_140	Lichens and mosses
BIO19	Precipitation of Coldest Quarter	lc_150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)
GROW	Length of vegetation growing period	lc_152	Sparse shrub (<15%)
SUNRAD	Sun radiation	lc_153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)
SNOW	Snow cover	lc_160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water
HFP	Human Footprint Index	lc_180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water
NUT	Administrative level	lc_190	Urban areas
ALT	Mean altitude	lc_200	Bare areas
AREA	Area of sampling unit	lc_201	Consolidated bare areas
Eu	Percentage of <i>Eucalyptus sp.</i>	lc_202	Unconsolidated bare areas
x_scale	Scaled X coordinate of the centroid of the unit area	lc_210	Water bodies
y_scale	Scaled Y coordinate of the centroid of the unit area	lc_220	Permanent snow and ice

b. Study area

The study area is the same as the previous report (ENETWILD consortium et al., 2022). It includes all countries in mainland Europe with the Ural Mountains as the eastern limit, spans 11,019,700 km² (110,197 10x10 km grid cells) and excludes Mediterranean islands, the UK, and Ireland, as well as the areas north to the distribution range of wild boar.

c. Methodology

i. Hunting yield model

The response variable for modelling wild boar HY was HY density across Europe (maximum number of individuals annually hunted within 2015-2025 hunting seasons, divided by unit area in km²; hereafter HY). Therefore, as the data selected represent the maximum potential, they generally refer to records from before the arrival of African swine fever in the affected regions. We followed the generic framework developed by ENETWILD consortium et al. (2021, 2022) for wild boar. The eco-geographical predictors more relevant in explaining HY were determined using a generalized linear model (negative binomial distribution and logarithmic link function; Cameron & Trivedi 2013).

Following steps were the same as in previous reports. Multicollinearity among predictors was assessed using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF); predictors with VIF values above 2 were removed (Zuur et al., 2010).

All models were trained using an 80% random sample of the data (training dataset) and model predictions were validated against the remaining 20% of the data (validation dataset). The final models were obtained using forwards-backwards stepwise procedure based on Akaike Information Criteria (AIC; Akaike 1974).

After modelling, calibration plots were developed to assess the predictive performance of the model. This was carried out by plotting the mean observed HY in each interval (defined from **percentiles**) of the predicted HY on the validation dataset, and thus perfect predictions should lie along the identity line (Pearce & Ferrier, 2001), where monotonicity of the relationship informs about the reliability of the predicted pattern. Moreover, we divided the validation data into the four bioregions to assess if the model fit differed among bioregions and used the calibration dataset with and without 0 density values.

Model output was statistically downscaled to make predictions at 10x10km using EAA grid (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/eea-reference-grids-2>).

ii. Model calibration into densities

Wild boar densities obtained in the framework of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW) based on camera trapping, as well as some from recent the literature (2015 onwards, see Figure 6 and Table 2 including reliable densities as recommended by ENETWILD consortium et al. 2021). Concretely, 110 values of density were used where hunting is practiced and free of African Swine Fever. For each location, the median values of the predicted densities of hunted animals were extracted at buffers of 5, 10 and 15 km radii respectively (three spatial resolutions).

General linear mixed models were parameterized using the densities values (log transformed) as response variable, and surface of the sampling location (in hectares and log transformed) and hunting yield (HYs), log transformed) as fixed factors. The bioregion was included as random effect factor. Models for different spatial resolutions were compared using AIC. The

most parsimonious model was used as reference to rescale HYs in wild boar population densities at European scale and 10x10 km spatial resolution.

Figure 1. Locations (green dots, n=110) where wild boar densities were obtained in the framework of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW, as well as some from recent the literature (two study sites in Norway and Sweden).

Table 2. Wild boar densities obtained in the framework of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW), as well as some from recent the literature (2012 onwards).

Country	Name study site	Administrative figure	Bioregion	Area (ha)	LON	LAT	Year	Density values (ind/km ²)	CV (%)	Method density
Albania	Çajupi Mountain	Protected Area	Western	2448	20.1500	42.0500	2021	1.50	32.67	REM EOW
Andorra	Vall de Ransol	Hunting ground	Western	2813	1.6400	42.6000	2023	2.61	43.70	REM EOW
Andorra	Ordino Valley	Protected Area	Southern	3660	1.5200	42.6300	2024	3.29	33.92	REM EOW
Armenia	Artavan	Protected Area	Eastern	1300	46.6100	39.6500	2023	0.80	54.80	REM EOW
Belarus	Naliboki Forest	Hunting ground	Eastern	1410	26.4700	53.9300	2021	7.41	24.83	REM EOW
Belgium	Game Management Unit 8	Protected Area	Western	3700	4.6708	50.8122	2024	4.54	36.57	REM EOW
Belgium	Marche-en-Famenne	Military camp	Western	2500	5.3700	50.2500	2023	39.73	17.00	REM EOW
Bosnia&Herzegovina	Romanija	Forestry	Western	6000	18.4900	43.5600	2023	0.60	33.00	REM EOW
Bulgaria	Panagyurishte	Hunting ground	Eastern	3600	24.4200	42.4900	2021	2.51	66.53	REM EOW
Bulgaria	Voden	Hunting ground	Eastern	8000	26.6830	43.6650	2024	3.13	31.90	REM EOW
Croatia	Biokovo	Hunting ground	Eastern	2000	17.0500	43.3300	2021	0.35	68.57	REM EOW
Croatia	Prolom	Hunting ground	Eastern	7700	16.1000	45.2500	2023	15.30	14.28	REM EOW
Czech Republic	Bohemian Switzerland NP	Protected Area	Eastern	8000	14.3800	50.8800	2024	1.00	53.87	REM EOW
Czech Republic	Jizerské Mts.	Hunting ground	Eastern	3761	14.4400	50.8300	2023	1.80	34.00	REM EOW
Czech Republic	Niva	Hunting ground	Eastern	2000	16.8500	49.4500	2021	17.09	43.42	REM EOW
France	Marais Noir de Saint-Coulban	Protected & hunting ground	Western	1500	-1.9100	48.5700	2022	2.61	49.63	REM EOW
Georgia	Lagodekhi NP	Hunting ground	Eastern	2445	46.3160	41.8769	2022	1.12	44.64	REM EOW
Georgia	Lukhuni	Protected Area	Western	4000	43.2961	42.7819	2024	0.42	87.88	REM EOW
Georgia	Machakhela NP	Protected Area	Western	7359	41.8300	41.4800	2023	4.36	44.30	REM EOW
Georgia	Mtiralala NP	Protected Area	Western	1580	41.8500	41.6600	2023	0.15	63.04	REM EOW
Germany	Alt Oerrel	Hunting ground	Western	4130	10.2000	52.9600	2021	3.38	35.21	REM EOW
Germany	Bavarian Forest NP	Protected Area	Western	1423	13.4527	48.9346	2024	3.24	31.06	REM EOW
Germany	Siebengebirge	Protected & hunting ground	Western	3346	7.2760	50.6566	2024	2.75	33.26	REM EOW
Germany	Süsing	Hunting ground	Western	2720	10.3300	53.0900	2021	2.31	37.66	REM EOW

Hungary	Gemenc	Forestry	Eastern	2000 0	18.8735	46.2178	202 4	3.79	29.63	REM EOW
Italy	Alpe di Catenaiia	Protected Area	Western	2700	11.9123	43.6674	202 4	16.32	21.37	REM EOW
Italy	Appennino Lucano	Protected Area	Southern	2500 0	15.9970	40.2542	202 4	18.79	25.46	REM EOW
Italy	CACN3	Hunting ground	Western	7300 0	7.0983	44.4905	202 1	5.84	36.30	REM EOW
Italy	Mandria	Protected Area	Western	1604	7.5600	45.1700	202 4	22.52	27.46	REM EOW
Italy	Marcarolo	Protected Area	Western	8288	8.7903	44.5529	202 4	0.96	29.00	REM EOW
Italy	San Rossore	Protected Area	Western	4650	10.3185	43.7131	202 4	39.36	24.33	REM EOW
Italy	Varzi	Hunting ground	Western	2660 0	9.1964	44.8229	202 4	1.78	37.27	REM EOW
Italy	Zona Bianca	Hunting ground	Western	6033	9.0200	45.0600	202 3	1.62	35.00	REM EOW
Montenegro	Bjelasica Mountain	Protected Area	Western	5650	19.6099	42.8950	202 4	2.21	34.21	REM EOW
Montenegro	Orjen Mountain	Hunting ground	Western	6000	18.5500	42.6200	202 2	2.85	58.82	REM EOW
Netherlands	Veluwe	Forestry	Western	9000	5.7000	52.2000	202 4	4.47	43.85	REM EOW
Poland	Gora Kalwaria	Hunting ground	Eastern	4655	21.2000	51.9800	202 1	7.66	60.44	REM EOW
Poland	Niepolomice	Hunting ground	Eastern	5300	20.3960	50.0388	202 4	0.60	39.05	REM EOW
Portugal	Arrábida	Protected Area	Southern	3628 3	-9.0300	38.5200	202 2	18.44	34.46	REM EOW
Portugal	Bicas da Serra	Hunting ground	Southern	1129	-7.9300	37.2000	202 2	16.26	39.65	REM EOW
Portugal	Castelo Melhor	Hunting ground	Southern	3329	-7.0800	41.0400	202 2	1.95	38.14	REM EOW
Portugal	Castreja	Hunting ground	Southern	2470	-8.1400	42.0400	202 2	6.38	41.44	REM EOW
Portugal	Cubeira	Hunting ground	Southern	1812	-7.2200	39.6800	202 2	6.74	21.66	REM EOW
Portugal	Freguesia de Vimioso	Hunting ground	Southern	4911	-6.5246	41.5840	202 4	3.34	33.51	REM EOW
Portugal	Herdade da Coitadinha	Hunting ground	Southern	995	-7.0392	38.1743	202 4	4.04	22.73	REM EOW
Portugal	Homem-Pedra	Hunting ground	Southern	2019	-6.9086	40.3365	202 4	2.77	37.76	REM EOW
Portugal	Lombada	Hunting ground	Southern	2118 4	-6.6100	41.8600	202 2	2.79	40.12	REM EOW
Portugal	Médio Côa	Hunting ground	Southern	5018	-6.9906	40.4394	202 4	0.48	31.15	REM EOW
Portugal	Murça	Hunting ground	Southern	6404	-6.6100	41.8600	202 2	2.07	37.12	REM EOW
Portugal	Sudoeste	Hunting ground	Southern	6142	-8.7500	37.7600	202 2	19.94	42.21	REM EOW
Portugal	Tolosa	Hunting ground	Southern	4695	-7.7400	39.4100	202 2	2.92	29.55	REM EOW

Portugal	ZCA Santulhão	Hunting ground	Southern	2948	-6.6410	41.5730	2024	3.61	42.12	REM EOW
Serbia	Studenica	Hunting ground	Eastern	11000	20.2631	43.3320	2024	1.71	36.29	REM EOW
Slovakia	Cerová highlands	Hunting ground	Eastern	5500	20.1000	48.2200	2024	6.49	38.06	REM EOW
Slovakia	Javorie	Forestry	Eastern	10000	19.1400	48.5300	2022	4.73	46.00	REM EOW
Slovenia	Oljka	Hunting ground	Western	2637	15.0300	46.3400	2023	6.00	50.00	REM EOW
Slovenia	Rizana	Hunting ground	Western	3675	13.8540	45.5380	2024	6.95	41.71	REM EOW
Slovenia	Sinji vrh	Hunting ground	Western	4279	15.1595	45.4587	2024	4.54	37.21	REM EOW
Slovenia	Strunjan Park	Hunting ground	Western	3319	13.6440	45.4700	2024	3.78	32.27	REM EOW
Slovenia	Vrhe Vrabče	Hunting ground	Western	3950	13.9400	45.7800	2022	7.13	35.00	REM EOW
Spain	Agres	Protected Area	Southern	1632	0.517472	38.769232	2024	4.19	29.83	REM EOW
Spain	Arriola	Hunting ground	Southern	4000	2.389222	42.940055	2024	8.39	25.32	REM EOW
Spain	Avila	Hunting ground	Southern	2700	-5.6133	40.3818	2017	1.89	51.32	REM EOW
Spain	Barbadillo de Herreros	Hunting ground	Southern	7200	-3.2754	42.1710	2024	5.53	18.34	REM EOW
Spain	Boumort	Hunting ground	Southern	13000	1.0436	42.2484	2023	4.55	27.85	REM EOW
Spain	Cabanes-Torreblanca	Protected Area	Southern	850	0.1600	40.1400	2022	41.55	38.81	REM EOW
Spain	Canales de la Sierra	Hunting ground	Southern	6053	-3.0107	42.1589	2024	19.37	23.14	REM EOW
Spain	Huelva	Hunting ground	Southern	2200	-6.3931	37.9111	2022	3.48	46.55	REM EOW
Spain	Carcelén	Hunting ground	Southern	3193	-1.2795	39.0422	2024	2.41	33.09	REM EOW
Spain	Carche	Protected Area	Southern	5942	-1.1640	38.4270	2024	2.05	30.63	REM EOW
Spain	Casas Nuevas	Hunting ground	Southern	2000	-1.6920	38.8964	2021	2.52	39.29	REM EOW
Spain	Cazorla	Hunting ground	Southern	10300	-2.9394	37.9103	2023	3.21	28.24	REM EOW
Spain	Culebra	Hunting ground	Southern	8906	-6.4951	41.9656	2024	4.73	49.99	REM EOW
Spain	Daimiel	Protected Area	Southern	4337	-3.7300	39.1291	2024	6.31	28.07	REM EOW
Spain	Despeñaperros	Protected Area	Southern	7840	-3.5610	38.4105	2023	7.29	16.32	REM EOW
Spain	Doñana	Protected Area	Southern	6500	-6.4437	36.9895	2024	6.46	36.40	REM EOW
Spain	Ejulve	Hunting ground	Southern	6042	-0.5305	40.7146	2024	6.93	33.80	REM EOW

Spain	Caceres	Hunting ground	Southern	2456	-6.8982	39.4042	202 ₂	2.63	29.28	REM EOW
Spain	Leitzaran	Hunting ground	Southern	3493	-1.9500	43.1600	202 ₃	2.95	21.60	REM EOW
Spain	Lugo	Hunting ground	Western	3000	-7.6909	42.7852	202 ₁	5.78	25.78	REM EOW
Spain	Majadas	Hunting ground	Southern	2917	-1.9329	42.2954	202 ₄	0.82	24.49	REM EOW
Spain	Montgó	Protected Area	Southern	2086	0.1722	38.8011	202 ₄	8.44	21.35	REM EOW
Spain	Montseny	Protected Area	Southern	3000	2.4000	41.7993	202 ₄	7.78	26.34	REM EOW
Spain	Serra Calderona	Protected Area	Southern	2461	-0.4861	39.6665	202 ₄	4.25	25.02	REM EOW
Spain	Serra d'Irta	Protected Area	Southern	2690	0.2872	40.2904	202 ₄	11.83	28.12	REM EOW
Spain	Desert de les Palmes	Protected Area	Southern	3096	0.0400	40.0700	202 ₃	24.03	22.60	REM EOW
Spain	Parc Natural Hondo	Protected Area	Southern	994	-0.7813	38.1963	202 ₄	7.02	23.30	REM EOW
Spain	Pastoriza	Hunting ground	Western	8500	-7.3470	43.3489	202 ₃	1.29	33.13	REM EOW
Spain	Quatretonda	Hunting ground	Southern	2918	-0.3814	38.9647	202 ₄	14.12	18.56	REM EOW
Spain	Quintos de Mora	Hunting ground	Southern	6700	-4.0650	39.4133	202 ₄	9.57	22.99	REM EOW
Spain	Rala	Hunting ground	Southern	6748	-1.2806	42.8143	202 ₄	16.07	19.68	REM EOW
Spain	Resinera	Hunting ground	Southern	1700	-3.8315	36.9010	202 ₃	3.83	27.26	REM EOW
Spain	Riaño	Hunting ground	Western	7895	-5.1162	43.0716	202 ₄	2.25	30.80	REM EOW
Spain	Riglos	Hunting ground	Southern	2500	-0.6400	42.3700	202 ₁	11.31	36.34	REM EOW
Spain	Riofrio	Hunting ground	Southern	6141	-4.5000	39.1000	202 ₂	4.88	38.93	REM EOW
Spain	Rosario	Hunting ground	Southern	2000	-4.4182	39.1033	202 ₄	7.95	36.28	REM EOW
Spain	S Nieves	Protected Area	Southern	2730	-4.9734	36.7377	202 ₄	2.32	24.83	REM EOW
Spain	Sabaiza Navarra	Hunting ground	Southern	3500	-1.2806	42.8143	201 ₈	3.55	44.79	REM EOW
Spain	Saja	Hunting ground	Western	5629	-4.3742	43.3090	202 ₃	1.59	28.16	REM EOW
Spain	Sierra Espuña	Protected Area	Southern	6500	-1.5198	37.8530	202 ₄	1.99	44.35	REM EOW
Spain	Solanillos	Hunting ground	Southern	2800	-2.2100	40.9700	202 ₄	4.65	14.91	REM EOW
Spain	Sueve	Hunting ground	Western	1800	-5.2230	43.4522	201 ₈	2.19	22.83	REM EOW
Spain	Tirig	Hunting ground	Southern	1200	0.0214	40.4311	202 ₂	0.86	77.91	REM EOW
Spain	Utxesa	Protected Area	Western	1042	0.51822 ₃	41.4964	202 ₄	17.76	39.07	REM EOW

Spain	Valmayor	Hunting ground	Southern	4113	-4.2309	38.4064	2022	12.39	33.41	REM EOW
Spain	Amurrio	Hunting ground	Western	6219	-2.9645	43.0422	2020	2.12	39.15	REM EOW
Sweden	Stalbo	Hunting ground	Northern	2500	17.1200	60.0200	2022	2.81	114.79	REM EOW
Turkey	Kartdag Wildlife Reserve	Protected Area	Southern	12000	33.3400	41.7800	2023	2.25	38.50	REM EOW
Norway	Halden & Aremark	Hunting ground	Eastern	90000	11.6075	59.1629	2021	0.72	52.78	REM literature (Odden et al. 2022)
Sweden	Kolmården	Hunting ground	Eastern	5000	16.4144	58.7924	2019	1.60	28.75	REM literature (Triumf 2023)

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. The updated HY-based model

The calibration plots of wild boar (Figure 2) showed a good predictive performance for all bioregions.

Figure 2. Calibration plot for assessing predictive performance of wild boar HY model for each bioregion. Plots show the relationship between the predicted hunting yield densities (HY) and the observed ones on the validation datasets.

HY density (individual hunted per Km²) of wild boar at 10x10km are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Hunting yield (HY) density (individual hunted per Km²) of wild boar at 10x10km. Red areas are beyond the environmental domain according to MESS analyses. The window on the right shows the bioregion classification for further discussion purposes. Red areas are beyond the environmental domain according to MESS analyses.

The updated HY-based model shows robust predictive performance across bioregions, confirming the suitability of hunting yield data as a proxy for spatial variation in wild boar abundance. The monotonic calibration relationships and the agreement between predicted and observed values indicate that the modelling framework remains stable when updated with

recent datasets. This reinforces previous *ENETWILD* findings that HY data, when sufficiently detailed spatially, can capture broad-scale ecological gradients shaping wild boar distribution.

The improvement observed in northern Europe (particularly Fennoscandia) highlights the importance of recent increases in spatial resolution and data completeness. In these regions, the integration of finer-scale hunting statistics has reduced uncertainty and improved model calibration, demonstrating how data quality directly translates into predictive reliability. We confirm a similar that previously reported pattern in southern Europe, where long-term *ENETWILD* data collection has ensured relatively consistent coverage, leading to stable predictions across successive model iterations.

In contrast, persistent inconsistencies in Central Europe, especially in France and Germany, illustrate the structural dependence of model performance on data availability. These discrepancies are unlikely to reflect ecological anomalies, but rather uneven reporting resolution and access to high-quality HY datasets. This reinforces the broader conclusion that modelling improvements at continental scale are increasingly constrained not by methodological limitations but by heterogeneity in upstream data provision.

Overall, the model confirms the value of maintaining a dynamic, iterative modelling framework, where incremental improvements in data coverage progressively enhance predictive performance.

3.2. Calibration of hunting yield-based model into densities

A summary of the general linear models parameterized for each spatial resolution using HYS log transformed as responses variable and the reliable densities values from EOW (log transformed), and surface of the sampling location (in hectares and log transformed) as fixed factors are shown in Table 2 (see Table 1 for wild boar densities obtained in the framework of the EOW).

Table 2. Summary of the general lineal models parameterized for each spatial resolution. Akaike Information Criteria (AIC), including R^2 . Densities values from EOW (log transformed) were the response variable, and surface of the sampling location (in hectares and log transformed) and HYS log transformed as fixed factors and the bioregion were random effect factor).

Spatial resolution	AIC	R^2
5km	89.5	20.6
10km	84.7	19.2
15km	93.1	15.6

The best model fitted for 10 km radius buffer was selected. The statistical parameters of the model are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. The statistical parameters of the model for 10km radius.

	Estimate	t-value	p-value
Intercept	2.13	0.40	***
log(surface)	-0.14	-0.04	***

log(Densities)	0.16	0.06	*
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The representation of the statistical relationships between reliable wild boar densities and predicted HY (fitted for 15km radius) can be seen in Figure 4, and resemble that obtained by *ENETWILD*-Consortium (2022).

Figure 4. Representation of the statistical relationships between reliable wild boar densities and predicted HY (fitted for 10km radius).

The Figure 5 displays the calibrated wild boar density values (predictions) at 10x10km resolution. The modelled wild boar density estimation is provided as a geopackage (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20072207>) and was obtained by fitting the surface of the study area to the median value in the dataset.

Predicted densities Wild Boar indiv/km²

Figure 5. Map showing the predicted pre-ASF wild boar density (10x10 km resolution) after the calibration of predicted hunting yields-based abundance on a set of reliable density values for Europe.

The calibration of HY predictions into density estimates further increases the operational relevance of the model. By translating relative abundance into density metrics, the outputs become directly usable for epidemiological and risk-assessment applications, particularly in the context of African swine fever, as previously done (*ENETWILD*-consortium 2024). However, uncertainty remains associated with the limited number of calibration sites and the assumption of transferability across bioregions, which should be addressed in future updates through expanded density datasets and continued validation efforts.

3. Conclusions and further steps

- The updated HY-based wild boar model provides an improved and operationally relevant representation of abundance patterns across Europe, consolidating its role as a reference layer for risk assessment and wildlife management.

- First, the model confirms improved predictive performance in regions where high-resolution and recent hunting yield data are available, particularly in Fennoscandia, while also demonstrating the stability of predictions in southern Europe where long-term datasets already exist. This indicates that the modelling framework is mature and that future gains will primarily depend on data improvements rather than methodological changes.
- Second, the persistence of prediction uncertainty in Central Europe highlights the critical importance of engaging new data providers and improving spatial resolution of hunting statistics in these regions. Addressing this gap represents the main priority for future model refinement and for achieving a more homogeneous European coverage.
- Third, the successful calibration of HY predictions into density estimates substantially enhances the applicability of the model, allowing its integration into spatial risk analyses for African swine fever and other wildlife-related epidemiological processes. The model therefore represents a key component of the European wildlife analytical infrastructure.

Future work should focus on:

- Expanding the network of reliable density estimates for calibration,
- Improving temporal consistency to enable trend analyses,
- Strengthening collaboration with data providers in under-represented regions, and
- Maintaining regular model updates as new data become available.

Overall, the present update demonstrates that the *ENETWILD* modelling framework is operationally robust and scalable, and that continued investment in data harmonisation and provider engagement will be the main driver of future improvements.

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